

Prevalence of Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome Using a Single Hop Test in Active Individuals

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Abstract

Background - Medial tibial shin syndrome (MTSS), commonly referred to as shin splint, is a frequent lower limb overuse injury, especially among physically active individuals. It presents as exercise induced pain along the medial border of tibia and is often linked to biomechanical overload and functional impairment. Early screening using functional performance test like the single hop test may help in identifying individuals at risk.

Materials and Methodology - This cross sectional observational study included 80 physically active individuals aged 20 to 50 years. Participants underwent a screening protocol including the single hop test, shin palpation for tenderness along the tibial border, the numerical rating scale (NRS) for pain intensity and the Lower extremity functional scale (LEFS) to assess functional limitations. The aim was to assess the prevalence of MTSS among these individuals and to correlate functional test performance with clinical signs and subjective scores

Results - Out of 80 active individuals assessed, the Single Hop Test identified 53 positive cases of MTSS (66.25%), while the Tibial Palpation Test found 51 positive cases (63.75%). Both findings showed a significantly higher prevalence than expected, indicating a notable burden of MTSS in the active population. However, statistical analysis (Fisher's Exact Test) revealed no significant association between the two tests, suggesting they assess different clinical aspects of MTSS. These results highlight the importance of using both tests in combination for effective screening.

Conclusion - The Single hop test, in combination with shin palpation and subjective scales such as NRS and LEFS, is effective in identifying the prevalence of Medial tibial shin syndrome in active individuals.

Keywords - Medial tibial shin syndrome, Single hop test, shin palpation, numerical rating scale, lower extremity functional scale.

● INTRODUCTION

Medial tibial stress syndrome (MTSS), commonly known as "shin splints," is a frequent injury of the lower extremity and one of the most common causes of exertional leg pain in athletes.¹ Other terms used for MTSS are shin splints, medial tibial shin syndrome, tibial stress syndrome, and soleus syndrome.² MTSS is a condition where pain is felt on the anterolateral or distal two third of the posteromedial aspect of tibia.³

Medial tibial stress syndrome (MTSS) is the discomfort and pain in the leg region due to repetitive pressure. It is one of the most common overuse issues in runners and the community, affecting almost 35% of the athletic population. Overuse injuries like MTSS can impact up to 70% of runners in a year⁴ and also overuse injuries, can account for 18.5% of all soccer-related disabilities.³ Incidence of MTSS

is reported as being 4% in military personnel.⁵ Prevalence of football for MTSS was 28.6% whereas for hockey 34.6%, cricketers 21.3% and in tennis players 20.0%⁶

Repetitive stress that generates microdamage beyond the repair threshold could be a mechanism for developing MTSS. Various types of bone stress differ from the appropriate stress of enough rest, which strengthens it.⁷ When bending pressure on the tibia is more significant than the strength of opposite leg muscles, it is considered MTSS. Periostitis and repetitive tibial bending and bowing have been associated with MTSS. Periostitis can be caused by several causes, including exercise intensity and training surfaces. Furthermore, a sudden increase in training volume on hard surfaces is a training error, and ageing footwear is the commonest cause of MTSS. According to the literature, there is a link between the deep posterior and anterior compartment fascia and the MTSS.⁸ Because periosteal traction can be caused by the soleus and tibialis posterior muscles, they are assumed to be implicated. It is also been hypothesized that flexor digitorum longus contractions put extra strain on the tibial fascia. Periosteum muscle traction can induce MTSS, with the soleus being the most common.⁹

Closed chain pronation occurring at the subtalar joint (STJ) involves eversion of the calcaneus and adduction and plantarflexion of the talus.¹⁰ Through articulations at the ankle subtalar and midtarsal joints, the location of the talus within the ankle mortise generates a coupling mechanism that transfers pronation of the foot into rotation of the tibia.¹¹

Other characteristics of medial tibial stress syndrome include pain during percussion and discomfort during hopping, it has been shown that the posteromedial border of the tibia is the most sensitive area.¹² Patients with this condition may also experience mild oedema and tibial line subcutaneous thickening. Localized pain, discomfort, and oedema are more likely to be brought on by stress fractures. As a result, they need to be medically excluded. Additionally, conditions such as tendinitis, compartment syndrome, popliteal artery compression, vasculitis, and nerve impingement are taken into account when evaluating people with medial tibial stress syndrome.

To assess for the prevalence of MTSS in active individuals, shin palpation test and single hop test is designed to evaluate their shin pain and to assess the severity of pain with the help of lower extremity functional scale the individual is asked to perform the component and after performing the individual is asked to score in between 0-10 with the help of NRS Scale. the functional evaluations are taken as:

The 10-point NUMERIC SCALE ranges from '0' representing one pain extreme (e.g. "no pain") to '10' representing the other pain extreme (e.g. "pain as bad as you can imagine" or "worst pain imaginable")

The Lower extremity functional scale (LEFS) is a questionnaire containing 20 questions about a person's ability to perform everyday tasks. The LEFS can be used by the clinicians as a measure of patient's initial function, ongoing progress and outcome.

A series of hop tests are routinely used in the assessment for return to Activities of daily living and sports post-injury, be it an ankle sprain, stress fracture or anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. They are both functional and quantitative, allowing a measurement of power and strength of the affected to unaffected leg.

- NEED OF STUDY-

1. The active individuals stand, runs, walks and climb staircase for a prolong period of time and frequently.

2. Despite of having biomechanical connection none of the studies have highlighted the prevalence of MTSS in active individual, therefore the purpose of the study is to find out prevalence of active individuals suffering from MTSS.

- AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. AIM- To find prevalence of MTSS in active individuals.

2. OBJECTIVES- 1. To find prevalence of MTSS in active individuals using single hop test and tibial palpation method

2. To measure the severity of pain using NRS and the person's ability to perform everyday task by using LEFS scale.

- REVIEW OF LITERATURE-

- 1) James Becker, Stanley James, Robert Wayner, Louis Osternig, Li-Shan Chou conducted a study on "Biomechanical Factors Associated with Achilles Tendinopathy and Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome in Runners" stated that Forty-two runners participated in this study (13 with AT, 8 with MTSS, and 21 matched controls). Participants were evaluated for lower extremity alignment and flexibility, after which a 3-dimensional kinematic and kinetic running gait analysis was performed. Differences between the 2 injuries and between injured and control participants were evaluated for flexibility and alignment, rearfoot kinematics, and 3 ground-reaction force metrics. Binary logistic regression was used to evaluate which variables best predicted membership in the injured group.

This concluded that compared with healthy controls, runners currently symptomatic with MTSS have a longer duration of eversion but not greater excursion or velocity of eversion.

- 2) Marinus Winters, Maarten H Moen, Wessel O Zimmermann, Robert Lindeboom, Adam Weir, Frank JG Backx conducted a study on "The medial tibial stress syndrome score: a new patient-reported outcome measure" stated that A prospective cohort study was performed in multiple sports medicine, physiotherapy and military facilities in the Netherlands. Participants with MTSS filled out the previously generated items for the MTSS score on 3 occasions. From previously generated items, we selected the best items. We assessed the MTSS score for its validity, reliability and responsiveness. This concluded that The MTSS score is a valid, reliable and responsive PROM to measure the severity of MTSS. It is designed to evaluate treatment outcomes in clinical studies

- 3) Mark F. Reinking, Tricia M. Austin, Randy R. Richter and Mary M. Krieger conducted a study on Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome in Active Individuals: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Risk Factors stated that Female sex, increased weight, higher navicular drop, previous running injury, and greater hip external rotation with the hip in flexion are risk factors for the development of MTSS.

4) Megan E. Sievers, Andrew M. Busch EdD conducted a study on Medial tibial stress syndrome: The relationship between gender and lower-extremity functional performance among collegiate track and field athletes stated that, this study aimed to examine lower extremity differences among collegiate track and field athletes with and without a previous MTSS diagnosis, using five different functional tests. The tests were chosen due to their proven reliability in assessing the lower kinetic chain for functional movement. These measurements were time efficient, cost effective, and easy to administer in a limited space. This concluded that This study attempted to identify relationships among athletes with previous MTSS diagnoses using five lower-extremity functional tests in Division III track and field athletes. Females had significantly more previous MTSS diagnoses while exhibiting significant balance deficits compared to males. Subjects with a history of MTSS were not found to differ in ankle DF, SLAR, SLBAL, or SLH performances when compared to those with no history of MTSS. Previous MTSS diagnosis was found to significantly increase the chances of re-injury by a factor of 17.3. This data extends knowledge of the effects of previous injury on future injury and potential effects of gender on the development of MTSS.

- HYPOTHESIS

1. null hypothesis

- There will be no significant prevalence of MTSS in active individuals

2. research hypothesis

- There will be significant prevalence of MTSS in active individuals

- MATERIALS

1. Pen/Pencil

2. Data record sheet

3. Outcome measure - single hop test

4. Tape and Tape measure

5. Shin palpation method- plinth

6. Stop watch

7. Scale- numerical rating scale and lower extremity functional scale

- **METHODOLOGY**

1. study design

- Type of study- Cross sectional study
- Duration of study- 18 months
- Place of study- metropolitan city

2. sample design

- Sample population- Active individuals
- Sample size- 80 individuals
- Sampling type- Convenient sampling

- **SELECTION CRITERIA**

- 1. INCLUSION CRITERIA**

1. Individuals who are willing to participate
2. Female and male both can participate
3. Age-20-50 years
4. Long standing individuals
5. Pain while walking and at rest
6. Unilateral and bilateral pain

- 2. EXCLUSION CRITERIA**

1. Any previous history of knee pain
2. History of lower limb fracture or ankle ligament damage in the previous 6 months
3. Impair sensation and/or pain perception related to diabetes, PVD, local infection, RA and gout
4. Complaining of acute fracture and sprains

- PROCEDURE

- Selection of the subject will be done as per inclusion and exclusion criteria
- A written informed consent will be taken from the subjects in the language best understood to them.
- Further subjects who are willing to participate will be included in this study
- Purpose of this study and procedure will be explained to them
- Demographic data will be taken and BMI will be measured by height and body weight
- NRS scale will be used to identify the level of pain
- Lower extremity functional scale will be used to assess person's ability to perform everyday tasks
- Single hop test-In this test, the aim is to jump as far as possible on a single leg, without losing balance and landing firmly. The distance is measured from the start line to the heel of the landing leg. The goal is to have a less than 10% difference in hop distance between the injured limb and uninjured limb.
- Shin palpation for pain and oedema was conducted with the subject in supine and the knee flexed in 90degrees and the foot on examination. Place of palpation was determined by marking two-third of the distal medial surface of tibia. Presence of pain was assessed by palpating the posteromedial border of tibia and presence of oedema was assessed by 5 seconds hold of the medial tibial surface.

- DATA INTERPRETATION AND STASTICAL ANALYSIS:

Collected data was entered in Microsoft excel and was used for the data analysis.

In this study, 80 active individuals were assessed to determine the prevalence of Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome (MTSS). The sample included both males and females with varying BMI, LEFS scores and NRS scale. Two methods were used to detect the presence of MTSS: Tibial Palpation and the Single Hop test

➤ Prevalence of MTSS using Single Hop test

Among the 80 participants assessed during the single hop test:

- 53 individuals were positive for MTSS.
- 27 individuals were negative.

The observed prevalence of MTSS using this method was 66.25% indicating that more than half of the active individuals in this study population showed positive findings when tested with the single hop test. Statistical analysis confirmed that this prevalence was significantly higher than expected, suggesting a notable presence of MTSS in the sample when using this method.

Total Individuals for Single hop test	MTSS Positive	MTSS Negative
80	53	27

Prevalence of MTSS (Single Hop Test)

➤ Prevalence of MTSS using Tibial Palpation

- When MTSS was assessed using Tibial Palpation:
- 51 Individuals tested using positive
- 29 individuals tested negative
- The prevalence observed using tibial palpation was 63.75% which again highlights a high rate of MTSS positivity among active individuals. This finding was statically significant confirming the diagnostic relevance of tibial palpation in identifying MTSS cases.

Total Individuals for tibial palpation	MTSS positive	MTSS negative
80	51	29

Prevalence of MTSS (Tibial Palpation)

➤ Association Between Single Hop Test and Shin Palpation

- To determine whether there was any relationship between the outcomes of the Single Hop Test and the Shin Palpation method, both test results were compared. Statistical analysis using Fisher’s Exact Test revealed:

- There was no significant association between the Single Hop Test and Shin Palpation results.

- This indicates that these two clinical tests function independently in detecting MTSS, and a positive result in one does not necessarily predict a positive result in the other.

	Single hop test	Shin palpation	Total
MTSS positive	53	51	104
MTSS negative	27	29	56
Total	80	80	160

- Discussion-

The current cross-sectional study investigated the prevalence of Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome (MTSS) in active individuals aged 20 to 50 years using clinical assessment tools: the Single Hop Test and Tibial Palpation, supported by the Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) and Lower Extremity Functional Scale (LEFS). Among 80 participants, MTSS prevalence was found to be 66.25% using the Single Hop Test and 63.75% via Tibial Palpation. Both outcomes were statistically significant when compared to the hypothesized baseline of 25%, indicating a high burden of MTSS in this population.

Historically, MTSS has been studied primarily in athletes and military populations. Reinking et al. (2016) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis, identifying risk factors such as higher body mass index (BMI), increased navicular drop, previous running injuries, and female sex. Similarly, Becker et al. (2017) observed prolonged rearfoot eversion among symptomatic runners, reinforcing the role of biomechanical abnormalities in MTSS etiology. Winters et al. (2015) validated a patient-reported outcome measure (MTSS score) to evaluate symptom severity, suggesting the importance of standardized clinical assessment.

In contrast to these studies, the present investigation focused on general active individuals—those who frequently walk, climb stairs, or stand for prolonged periods but are not necessarily athletes. This represents a unique and under-researched group. The high prevalence observed highlights the importance of considering MTSS even in non-sport populations, especially those engaged in repetitive lower limb loading due to occupational or lifestyle demands.

Furthermore, while both diagnostic tools in this study effectively identified MTSS cases, the Fisher's Exact Test indicated no statistically significant association between the Single Hop Test and Tibial Palpation ($p = 0.8685$). This suggests the two methods may capture different clinical aspects—functional asymmetry versus localized tenderness—supporting the utility of using both in combination. Hubbard et al. (2008) emphasized the multifactorial nature of MTSS and the need for a multi-modal assessment approach, a principle supported by our findings.

From a pathophysiological standpoint, MTSS involves repetitive traction-induced microtrauma and inflammation at the distal posteromedial tibial periosteum. Risk factors include overuse, excessive pronation, improper footwear, hard training surfaces, and weak posterior compartment muscles. Bates (1985) and DeLacerda (1980) previously described these features in athlete-focused populations, which this study confirms in active, non-athlete individuals.

The clinical implication is significant: MTSS is not exclusive to athletes but also affects the wider active adult population. Screening for early signs, especially in those with persistent shin pain, may help prevent progression to more severe conditions such as stress fractures. Emphasizing proper biomechanics, footwear, and strength training in preventive strategies is warranted.

- CONCLUSION

This study aimed to find the prevalence of Medial Tibial Stress Syndrome (MTSS) in active individuals using the Single Hop test and Shin Palpation Method. The study concluded that MTSS is commonly found in active individuals, especially those involved in prolonged standing, walking or running. The results showed a significantly high prevalence of MTSS, indicating the need for early screening.

- LIMITATIONS-

This study used convenient sampling from a metropolitan population, which may limit external validity. The absence of long-term follow-up also restricts the understanding of recurrence or chronicity. Future research should explore MTSS prevalence across different occupations, incorporate gait and muscle strength analysis, and evaluate the efficacy of preventive intervention

- OUTCOME MEASURE-
- NUMERICAL FUNCTIONAL SCALE

- LOWER EXTREMITY FUNCTIONAL SCALE

<i>Activities</i>		<i>Exteme Difficulty or Unable to Perform Activity</i>	<i>Quite a Bit of Difficulty</i>	<i>Moderate Difficulty</i>	<i>A Little Bit of Difficulty</i>	<i>No Difficulty</i>
a.	Any of your usual work, housework, or school activities.	0	1	2	3	4
b.	Your usual hobbies, recreational or sporting activities.	0	1	2	3	4
c.	Getting into or out of the bath.	0	1	2	3	4
d.	Walking between rooms.	0	1	2	3	4
e.	Putting on your shoes or socks.	0	1	2	3	4
f.	Squatting.	0	1	2	3	4
g.	Lifting an object, like a bag of groceries from the floor.	0	1	2	3	4
h.	Performing light activities around your home.	0	1	2	3	4
i.	Performing heaving activities around your home.	0	1	2	3	4
j.	Getting into or out of a car.	0	1	2	3	4
k.	Walking 2 blocks.	0	1	2	3	4
l.	Walking a mile.	0	1	2	3	4
m.	Going up or down 10 stairs (about 1 flight of stairs).	0	1	2	3	4
n.	Standinf for 1 hour.	0	1	2	3	4
o.	Sitting for 1 hour.	0	1	2	3	4
p.	Running on even ground.	0	1	2	3	4
q.	Running on uneven ground.	0	1	2	3	4
r.	Making sharp turns while running fast.	0	1	2	3	4
s.	Hopping.	0	1	2	3	4
t.	Rolling over in bed.	0	1	2	3	4
Column Totals:						

● SHIN PALPATION TEST-

SINGLE HOP TEST-

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